

PHYSICO - MECHANICAL CHARACTERISATION OF JUTE FIBRE COMPOSITES WITH THERMOSET RESIN

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SUMMARY : Several useful composite materials have been developed with natural fibre and plastic matrix and their commercial viability has been established for adding value to abundant and cheap natural resources. Macromolecular Research Centre, Jabalpur, India has recently developed jute fibre reinforced thermoset plastic composite wherein the matrix resin consists of resol type phenolic resin (PR) and bifunctional epoxy resin (EP) condensate. The laminates of jute fibre and PR-EP condensate were prepared by hot press moulding technique and the jute fibre weight fraction in these composites was varied from 0.4 to 0.8. The mechanical properties of selected ten jute fibre (PR-EP) condensate composites are reported for parameters like ultimate tensile strength, elongation, tensile modulus and flexural strength and modulus. The water uptake behavior of these composites was examined by constructing water absorption isotherm, and water diffusion coefficient and water absorption (24 h soak test) were determined.

KEY WORDS : Lignocellulose, Thermoset, Jute fibre, Hession Cloth, Phenolic, Epoxy, Prepreg.

INTRODUCTION

The opportunities offered by lignocellulosic composites – such as optimised performance, minimised weight and volume, cost effectiveness, fatigue and chemical resistance and resistance to biodegradation - are available to virtually every manufacturer. Researchers in the area of materials technology are showing increased interest in the benefits of composite technology. The objective of composite technology is to produce a product with performance characteristics that combine the beneficial aspects of each constituents. New composites are produced with an aim to either reduce the cost of production or to improve performance or both. Composites of natural fibre (like jute) reinforced thermoset plastics were primarily developed (Ref.1) for use as low cost housing materials, silos for grain storage and small finishing boats. These materials however, could not satisfy necessary technoeconomic criteria for large-scale commercial exploitation, and this was attributed to their high resin consumption and high moisture absorption. The resin poor composite had exhibited not very satisfactory mechanical, thermal and water sorption characteristics. The nonamenability to prepreg technique in jute fibre and thermoset resins used have restricted the large production of their composites and for the same reason, it was also not possible to realise the composite end products of intricate geometrical shape required for structural and other specific applications. Recently, composites having relatively high jute fibre weight fraction has been developed as cost effective alternatives to previously studied jute composites with high resin content (Ref.2). Macromolecular Research Centre, R.D.University, Jabalpur, India has initiated a programme on the development of a composite materials using waste newspaper

and a suitable resin matrix. The problem of compatibility of newspaper having cellulosic materials with resin matrix have been primarily addressed in this specific study. The matrix compositions of epoxy with phenolic resin were reported (Ref.3) wherein the novolac type of phenolic resin has been used as a curative of epoxy resin matrix. The advancement in the manufacturing techniques has led to the development of prepreg technique and the basic resin system should preferably be in homogenous liquid phase. From this consideration, the combination of phenolic resin with medium viscosity epoxy resin system may become very attractive. The resol phenolic resin has not been used as matrix resin due to their very short shelf life, the high reactive nature and evolution of volatile matter during its curing reaction. Of late, suitable modifications in the production of resol type phenolic resin have been made which have resulted in the development of the resin having long shelf life with moderate viscosity and which does not need any solvent.

A matrix resin consisting of a resol type phenolics and diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-A type epoxy resin has been chosen utilising the basic chemical reactions studied previously (Ref.3). The Hession (Jute cloth) based composites have been prepared from the resol phenolic-epoxy condensate prepreps wherein the jute fibre weight fraction has been varied from 0.40 to 0.80 and the two promising ratios of phenolic and epoxy resin viz. 2:1 and 1:1 (w/w) are used to prepare matrix resin to prepare jute fibre prepreps. The macroscopic mechanical properties (tensile, compressive and flexural strength and modulus) have been determined. The sample designation as JC-1 to JC-5 are prepared with phenolic-epoxy matrix with 2:1 (w/w) ratio and they contain the fibre weight fractions of 0.40, 0.50, 0.60, 0.70 and 0.80 respectively. The correlation of these properties with structural features of various components of jute fibre and matrix resin has been established. In light of the earlier reported major limitations in terms of sorption and desorption of moisture in high fibre weight fraction (above 0.40) jute composites, detailed water uptake characterisation have been undertaken. Total water uptake both in short and long terms were determined and sorption capacities are compared in terms of water diffusion coefficient determined experimentally. It may be concluded from the results obtained so far that the large-scale production of jute fibre reinforced thermoset composites exhibiting desirable properties is economically viable.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials:

Phenolic Resin : The phenol-formaldehyde resin used in the present study was PR-100, commercially available from ABR Organics Ltd. Hyderabad, India, which is solventless resol type phenolic resin. The total solid content in resin is 65-75% (w/w polymer) and 25-35% (w/w oligomer). The physicochemical characteristics of PR-100 resin are dark brown liquid, viscosity (30°C) = 0.6 to 0.9 Pa.S, pH = 7.5 to 7.8 and gel time at 150°C = 6 min.

Epoxy Resin : Diglycidyl ether of Bisphenol-A type epoxy resin (LAPOX B-11) was obtained from Cibatul Ltd. Mumbai, India which is basically unmodified resin. The LAPOX B-11 has epoxy value 5.2-5.5 equiv/kg and its viscosity at 25°C was 0.9 to 1.2 Pa.S.

Hession Cloth (Jute Fibre) : The general characteristics of jute fibre were (i) Basic weight = 35 g/m², (ii) No. of warp = 420 and weft = 450. No. of filament in a rowp = 125 (iii) Moisture content = 8 to 12 % (iv) Residue content = approximately 20%. The mechanical and other characteristics were neither reported nor determined in this laboratory.

Jute Composite Preparation : The prepregs of jute and phenol-formaldehyde and epoxy resin matrix was prepared in which the ratio of phenolic to epoxy resin was 100:50 (i.e., 50 parts of epoxy per hundred part of phenolic or php) and 100:100 (i.e., 100 parts of epoxy php of phenolic). The calculated quantity of uniformly mixed resin was coated over on either side of the jute and same was heated for 3 to 10 min at 140 to 170°C in heavy-duty oven. The resultant prepregs of jute and PR-EP were stacked in sufficient number to build up the composites thickness to 1.5 to 2 mm. The stacked prepregs were kept in three pieces leaky mould and pressure was applied to the mould. The Time-Temperature profile used for the curing was : 150°C for 1h and further 200°C for 3 hours. The mould was brought to room temperature for removing the sample. Jute composites were designated as JC-1 to JC-5 for 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7 and 0.8 fibre weight fraction respectively at constant PR-EP ratio of 100:50 and JC-6 to JC-10 for 0.3, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7 and 0.8 fibre weight fraction respectively at constant PR-EP ratio of 100:100.

Mechanical Characterisation : The determination of tensile strength, modulus and elongation was performed on Instron's Universal Testing Machine according to ASTM test method D-638. The cross head speed (initial strain rate) was 5mm/min and grip length was 80 mm. The flexural test were performed on Instron Universal Testing Machine according to ASTM test method D-790. The cross head speed and gauge length were kept 1.3mm/min and 25 mm respectively. The average of the five results were reported. Heat Deflection Temperature (HDT) was determined as per ASTM test method D-648 wherein the fibre stress was 1.81 MPa and the rate of heating was 2° per min. The span length was 100 mm. The average of the five results were reported.

Water Absorption, Absorption Isotherm and Diffusion Coefficient : Water absorption were determined as per ASTM test method D-570. The specimen of material were dried in an oven for 1h at 110°C and then the specimen were placed in a container of distilled water and the equilibrium values were determined at the end of 24 h. The water diffusion behaviour of the composites were determined by the method primarily developed by Shen & Springer (Ref.4) for moisture absorption of composite materials. A 30x32 mm specimen was cut from 2 mm thick composite. All the faces of the specimen were then polished to remove any surface roughness and the specimen was then dried to constant weight in oven at 100°C prior to testing. The samples were then kept in water for different interval of time and water absorbed at different interval of time and at equilibrium condition were determined. The moisture absorption isotherms for composites were obtained as a plot of water absorption against function of $\sqrt{\text{Time/Thickness}}$. From the gradient (m) of the linear portion of this isotherm curve, the diffusion coefficient for the composites was calculated using relationship given by Shen and Springer (Ref.4).

Density : Density was determined by the given equation

$$\text{Density (kg/m}^3\text{)} = \frac{f}{Lwt}$$

where,

- f = Oven dry weight (kg)
- L = Length of sample (m)
- w = Width of sample (m)
- t = Thickness of sample (m)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The cellulosic filler/fibre based composite with thermoplastics or thermoset matrix may exhibit the varied physicochemical properties depending upon the lignocellulosic content and the interaction between the filler and the matrix. The choice of matrix consisting of resol phenolic and epoxy resin for jute based composites fulfils these requirements to great extent. Being in liquid form, the combined phenolic-epoxy matrix may penetrate deep into the pores of the jute and may form a chemical bond with the lignocellulosic moieties present within and as well as on the surface of the jute. The interaction of the resin matrix and polar lignocellulosic fibre shall be critical in determining the properties (especially mechanical, water uptake) of the composite materials. It is expected that the phenolic epoxy combined matrix may have hydrogen bonding with hydroxyl groups of cellulose during the uncured stage and the strong covalent bonding may occur during the prepreg preparation or cure reaction of the matrix. The possible formation of covalent linkage between the hydroxyl functionality of the lignocellulosic materials of the jute with this resin matrix is being studied by FT-IR and other analytical instrument in our laboratory and will be reported shortly.

As mentioned earlier, the desired mechanical, physical (i.e. low water uptake and low density) and thermal properties are essential for structural and non-structural applications of these composites. The tensile and flexural strength and impact resistance are three major parameters which are generally evaluated for these composites with a view to assess their suitability for desired applications. In the present study, the tensile strength & modulus and flexural strength & modulus have been determined for ten jute fibre based composites wherein the resin matrix composition have been chosen at 50 and 100 parts of epoxy php. However, the weight fraction of the jute fibre has been varied from 0.4 to 0.8. It may also be noted that the jute fibre composites with phenolic-epoxy matrix were prepared with utmost care so that resin content was uniform throughout and as well as the volatiles were reduced to minimum for void free composite samples. The variation in tensile strength with increase in the weight fraction of jute fibre in composites is shown in Fig.1.

The tensile strength varies from 39.4 to 75.1 MPa for all the ten samples evaluated here. The highest tensile strength of 75.1 MPa is exhibited by composite having 100 parts of epoxy php and 0.4 fibre weight fraction whereas the lower tensile strength of 39.4 MPa is exhibited by

the composites having 0.8 weight fraction. The tensile modulus of these composites have shown declining trend with increase of the weight fraction of the jute fibre as can be seen from Fig.2. The tensile moduli of 14.2 GPa and 13.9 GPa were shown for jute fibre

weight fraction of 0.40 and 100 and 50 parts of epoxy php respectively, whereas lower tensile moduli for 10.7 GPa and 11.3 GPa for the higher jute fibre weight fraction (0.8). The decrease in both tensile strength and moduli with increase in jute fibre weight fraction is probably either due to the filler effect or insufficient chemical bond between resin matrix and fibre component of jute fibre. The later aspect, however, could not be authenticated for want of any experimental data available at the moment. The substantial improvement in tensile strength and moduli for 100 part of epoxy php could be explained by the formation of PR-EP adduct. The results of the effect on 'elongation at break' parameter with the increase of the jute fibre content in the composite have established that the elongation can be enhanced by reducing the resin matrix content in the composite. It can be seen from Fig.3 that the value of

elongation at break increases from 0.36 % at jute fibre weight fraction of 0.40 to the highest of 0.97 % at the weight fraction of 0.8 for the fifty part of epoxy php and same trend was

observed for 100 parts of epoxy php. These results suggest that the jute fibre component of the composite contributes more for the elongation value where the resin matrix plays important role in improving tensile strength and modulus.

The effect on both the flexural strength and flexural modulus with the variation of jute fibre weight fraction are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5 respectively. The increase in the jute fibre

weight fraction from 0.4 to 0.8 did not affect the flexural strength and the values are within $\pm 20\%$ from 130 MPa for initial jute fibre weight fraction (i.e. 0.4). Nevertheless, the steep reduction was observed at higher (0.7-0.8) jute fibre weight fraction for both 50 and 100 parts of epoxy php. It is evident from Fig.5 that the flexural modulus was found to be maximum at

0.4 and 0.5 jute fibre weight fraction and the further increase in the jute component has resulted in the reduction in flexural modulus values. The decrease in both flexural strength and flexural modulus in jute fibre based composite could be attributed to two different causes. The insufficient wetting of reinforcing material by the matrix resin could be one cause for the decrease in the flexural properties. However, the possibility of such situation

can be ruled out as the matrix resin was spread uniformly over the jute material and there was not much variation among the five samples prepared for each testing. As mentioned previously that phenolic epoxy matrix may form covalent bond with the hydroxyl groups of the cellulose moiety present in jute fibre. This possible formation of covalent linkage between hydroxyl functionality of lignocellulose material of jute fibre with the functional groups of matrix resin may cause the stoichiometric imbalance of the reactive components (i.e. phenolic and epoxy resins) of the resin matrix. It is, therefore, visualised that resultant composite material having the jute fibre weight fraction 0.4 to 0.5 might have desired stoichiometric compositions and thereby resulting in enhanced flexural properties. The resol type phenolic resin prepared by the reaction of phenolic and formaldehyde in alkaline conditions comprised of complicated mixtures of mono-or polynuclear hydroxymethyl phenols (Ref.5,6) and para-quinone methides (Ref.7). Since the resol type phenol-formaldehyde resin used in this study has been procured from commercial source, the actual phenol/formaldehyde ratio is not known. Due to the multiplicity of the reaction products it is very difficult to calculate the stoichiometric ratio of the phenolic and epoxy groups. This complexity is further increased due to the reaction of the matrix resin component with the reactive site of the lignocellulosic material. The overall results on the variation of the mechanical parameters with five different jute fibre weight fraction reflect the efficiency of prepreg method used in composite making as very consistent results were accomplished.

In recent years, there has been a shift towards the use of thermoplastic matrix (Ref.8) in place of thermoset resins for making the composites using cellulosic reinforcing fillers like jute fibre, wood fibre and flour. The use of thermoplastics may result in the ease of processing and also significant property advantage. However, the upper limit of service temperature for the use of such composites may be restricted to the lower temperature due to the low glass transition temperature of thermoplastics (polypropylene). Due to these constraints associated with thermoplastics, the use of thermoset resin like phenolics or epoxy shall offer advantage of the service temperature. Heat deflection temperature (HDT) is a property which would provide a basis for the selection of the material to be used at higher temperature. The HDT values for jute fibre based composites were determined and the results are shown in Fig.6.

The composites with the low jute fibre weight fraction (i.e. 0.4 and 0.5) have HDT of 155°C and 147°C respectively whereas there is a drastic reduction in HDT values at the jute fibre

weight fraction values of 0.5 onwards. The HDT of 110 to 121°C was observed for the composites having jute fibre weight fraction between 0.7 to 0.8. The reduction in HDT with increase in fibre content could be attributed to poor or insufficient encapsulation of the fibre with matrix resin and there exists the scope for improvement by adopting better prepreg preparation condition. These results on HDT of fibre based composites have demonstrated that the samples having lower jute fibre weight fraction or higher matrix content would be useful for higher temperature applications.

Water absorption and specific gravity of lignocellulosic fibre composite are two important physical properties that determine their end use applications. The water absorption by the composite materials could lead to a decrease in some of the properties like mechanical and thermal and this should be considered when selecting their end applications. It is difficult to entirely eliminate the absorption of moisture in the composite without using expensive surface barriers on the composite surface. Water adsorption in jute fibre based composite can lead to a build up of the moisture in the lignocellulosic fibre cell wall and also in the fibre-matrix interface region. The moisture build up in the cell wall could result in fibre swelling and affect the dimensional stability. These fibre based composites may give exposure to very high relative moisture and at times they may be in constant contact with water as in the rainy days. In light of these aspects, the water absorption, as determined by 24 h water soak test (ASTM-D-570) for these composites was determined. The water absorption coefficient was also determined for evaluating the relative water absorption capability of the jute fibre composites using phenolic-epoxy matrix. The water diffusion isotherms for jute fibre composite were constructed and from the gradient (m) of the linear portion of the curve, water diffusion coefficients of these materials were calculated using the relationship (as given in Equation-1) analytically worked out by Shen & Springer (Ref.4).

$$D = \pi \left[\frac{m h}{M_{\infty}} \right]^2 \left[1 + \left(\frac{h}{l} \right) + \left(\frac{h}{n} \right) \right]^2 \quad (1)$$

Where,

- D = Water diffusion coefficient corrected for edge effect
- m = Gradient of linear portion of the water content against $\sqrt{\text{Time/Thickness}}$ curve.
- M_{∞} = Equilibrium moisture content which is the value of the water absorbed that there is no further change in the water absorption with time
- h = Thickness
- l = Length
- n = Width

The consolidated data on percentage absorbed water determined as per ASTM-D-570 and the value of the water diffusion coefficients for jute composites are shown in Table-1. The water absorption by the composite sample was found dependence on its jute fibre weight fraction. The low water absorption was observed at jute fibre weight fraction of 0.4 and 0.5 and significant amount of water is getting absorbed at higher i.e. 0.7 to 0.8 jute weight fraction for 50 parts of epoxy php. The maximum water absorption of 23.19 at higher (i.e. 0.8) jute fibre weight fraction for 50 parts of epoxy php can itself be considered very low in comparison to jute fibre which absorbs over 100 % water within 2 to 3 h. The water diffusion coefficient for

the composite having jute fibre weight fraction of 0.4 was calculated to be $3.7 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$. It can be inferred that the sample JC-1 and JC-6 will be useful from the water absorption point of view. The end applications of these jute fibre reinforced phenolic-epoxy matrix need be selected on the basis of the water absorption characteristics. The values of Density for jute fibre composites (JC-1 to JC-10) are also given in Table-1.

Table 1 : Density, Water absorption and Diffusion Coefficient for Jute fibre composites

Sample Designation	Parts of Epoxy php	Fibre weight Fraction	Water uptake (24h) (%)	Water Sorption at Equilibrium condition (%)	Diffusion coefficient ($\times 10^{-4} \text{ mm}^2 \text{ S}^{-1}$)	Density (KgM^{-3})
JC-1	50	0.4	6.8	9.7	3.8	1120
JC-2	50	0.5	9.7	12.3	2.3	1140
JC-3	50	0.6	9.9	13.6	2.8	1150
JC-4	50	0.7	14.9	19.3	0.65	1180
JC-5	50	0.8	23.1	24.8	2.3	1190
JC-6	100	0.4	2.6	3.9	2.4	1195
JC-7	100	0.5	3.5	4.9	0.81	1188
JC-8	100	0.6	15.4	17.3	0.56	1144
JC-9	100	0.7	16.9	19.3	0.63	1188
JC-10	100	0.8	23.1	24.2	0.22	1200

Suchsland and Woodson (Ref.9) classified the wood or natural fibre board composites as per the density or specific gravity of end products and the same has been shown in Fig.7. It shows

Fig.7 : Classification of wood composite board by particle size, density and processing type (Ref. 9)

the raw material classifications of fibres, particles and veneers on the left-hand y-axis and shows the specific gravity on the x-axis. The right-hand y-axis describes in general terms the processing that takes place to produce a particular product and is classified either as wet or dry processed materials. According to this classification jute fibre composites comes in hard board range.

CONCLUSION

Jute fibre reinforced plastic composites are prepared wherein a matrix comprising resol type phenolics and epoxy resin is used as prepreg of reinforcing materials. The mechanical properties in respect of tensile strength and modulus, elongation at break, flexural strength and modulus and Heat Deflection Temperature (HDT) are determined for these composites containing jute fibre weight fraction varied from 0.4 to 0.8. The results of water absorption and diffusion coefficients of composites are determined and reported along with values of experimentally determined bulk density. The favorable thermomechanical and physicochemical properties of these jute fibre composites make them suitable for hard board materials.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors express their gratefulness to Dr.S.Setty, TIFAC, Dept. Of Science & Technology, Govt. of India for fruitful suggestions.

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